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RAMONES project's main objective is to close the current marine radioactivity under-sampling gap and foster new interdisciplinary research in ocean ecosystems. RAMONES will invest a significant effort to provide tools to enable long-term data acquisition missions, rapid deployments, low cost per information byte, and propose new AI and Robotics-driven and supported methodologies, being ambitious to eventually offer scaled-up solutions to researchers, policy makers and communities. All these may be achieved by combining state-of-the-art (SoA) methodologies and equipment from various disciplines in a well-balanced synergy, and designing new and effective methodologies targeting the marine environment, which will provide efficient response to existing natural and man-made hazards, and shape future policies for the global population. RAMONES will additionally contribute to shaping a blueprint on Environmental Intelligence in the EU and worldwide.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AHRS	Altitude and Heading references System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASV	Autonomous Surface Vehicle
ASWG	Autonomous Surface Wave Glider
AUG	Autonomous Underwater Glider
CMRE	Centre for Maritime Research & Experimentation
DEC	Distributed Estimation and Control
DEKF	Distributed Extended Kalman Filter
EIC	European Innovation Council
EU	European Union
EvINS	EvoLogics intelligent Networking Software
FET	Future and Emerging Technologies
GPS	Global Positioning System
IMS	Synchronous Instant Messages
LBL	Long Baseline
LPMIL	Low Profile Micro In Line (connector)
MAC	Media Access Control
NetMarSys	Simulation and Visualization of Distributed Autonomous Marine Robotic Systems
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PC	Personal Computer
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RTO	Real Time Offset
SLAP	Simultaneous Target Localization and Pursuit
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SoA	State of the Art
TNA	Transnational Access
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
USBL	Ultra-Short Baseline
UWA	Underwater Acoustic
WP	Work Package

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Abstract

RAMONES sets forth the innovative concept of autonomous, adaptive radioactivity monitoring using data acquired by a static benthic gamma laboratory and radiation instruments installed on board two off-the-shelf glider-type autonomous vehicles and an autonomous surface craft. The objective is to monitor large water volumes and offer appropriate behaviors based on on-line, event-driven decision-making processes in various scenarios. These vehicles, propelled mostly by environmental energy, can operate for extended periods of time in the ocean, in striking contrast to classical, medium-sized propelled robotic vehicles with reduced autonomy due to their energy hungry actuators and subsystems. Gliders are, therefore, key enabling tools given the requirements to acquire radiation-related measurements unattended for periods of days.

Due to their extreme low power requirements and low payload, gliders have rudimentary navigation systems, not compatible with the applications in mind. To address this issue, a positioning and communication system is described in this report based on ultra-short baseline acoustic devices. Moreover, to estimate quantities that are not directly measured and to improve the accuracy of the position estimates, preliminary concepts for cooperative navigation are also put forth in this report, exploiting inter-vehicle communication links and the use of relative range and/or bearing measuring units among vehicles, which may still be often available even if position fixes are not acquired.

Cooperative control is envisioned to afford the surface and underwater robotic platforms the capability to manoeuvre in a concerted manner, either following a pre-defined mission plan or generating the plan on-line, over successive time windows, in response to episodic events. Preliminary work is described on the development and implementation of selected methods for cooperative control and underwater target localization, followed by real tests with autonomous marine vehicles that are property of IST.

Finally, cooperative motion planning strategies are briefly discussed to avoid exhaustive search procedures, which are extremely demanding in terms of energy and preliminary work is described.

1. Introduction

Underwater acoustic (UWA) communications and positioning belong to are key components of the RAMONES system.

The project foresees the use of an Autonomous Surface Wave Glider (ASWG) as the **master communication and main geo-localisation node**, providing the possibility for the distribution of different data streams to other vehicles, as well as benthic and shore stations. Realization of the communications tasks requires development and implementation and integration (as part of the modem's firmware) of a number of innovative algorithms.

There are three large groups of tasks, which must be solved in the scope of the project:

- positioning tasks,
- communication tasks, and
- technical service tasks for simplification and acceleration of the development, e.g. provision and adaptation of the modem emulator and the acoustic channel simulator operating in virtual environment in a very similar way as in real underwater acoustic environment.

1.1 Positioning

The geo-localisation task involves the use of an underwater acoustic (UWA) modem combined with USBL antenna providing USBL positioning capabilities of the modem (so-called USBL-modem). The geo-localisation task involves also the use of new functionality, which is currently in development, for providing **synthetic LBL positioning** of the AUGs in relation to the geo-referenced benthic station. In the absence of full position fixes, the USBL-modem may still provide slant ranges between the AUGs and the benthic station. Instantaneously, these measurements do not suffice to retrieve the position of the AUGs. Nevertheless, they still bound the position of the AUGs to spheres, which is important information that can be used to bound the navigation error. Moreover, over a certain time span, and if accurate proprioception is possible, a synthetic long baseline may be constructed [Lar00], whereby the positions of the AUGs in different time instants emulate long baselines, and trilateration techniques may be applied to retrieve their positions. More advanced filtering techniques can also be employed to explore continues estimation without explicitly building the artificial long baselines [Bat11].

Moreover, the geo-localisation task will also include the use of additional new functionality for providing **synthetic LBL positioning** of AUGs by means of extensively manoeuvring ASWG. Similarly, to the synthetic LBL positioning system of the AUGs with respect to the benthic laboratory, a

synthetic LBL navigation system can also be devised with respect to the ASWG. This is, somehow, facilitated by the availability of GPS on-board the ASWG. However, good AUGs proprioception should also be available, and the relative movement should be rich enough to generate, over time, a virtual rich long baseline setting, whereby the relative positions of the AUGs with respect to the ASWG in different time instants effectively constitute the vertices of the LBL setting.

A set of **additional functionalities** is currently in development for facilitating **cooperative navigation** of the AUGs by estimating the state (positions and velocities) of multiple marine vehicles involved in a given mission **by means of inter-vehicle communication links** and by **measuring mutual ranges and/or bearings among vehicles**.

Thanks to data exchange between modems, several localisation techniques are planned to be implemented:

- localisation by means of USBL “synchronous” uni-directional transmissions and/or “asynchronous” bi-directional transmissions),
- (synchronous) range-only localisation, whereby slant ranges are feed directly to a tightly coupled navigation filter to bound the navigation error or even drive it to the vicinity of zero, depending on the available proprioception information and the richness of the trajectories,
- (“silent”) localisation through triangulation (note: not trilateration, but namely triangulation) using measurements of the USBL antenna, whereby bearing measurements, coupled with depth measurements, are used directly in a tightly coupled navigation filter to drive the navigation error to the vicinity of zero,

Positioning of the AUGs in geographic coordinates is anticipated to happen in relation to both ASWG and benthic station. ASWG has direct GPS access and the benthic station (after its position has been estimated) can be used as navigation aid. To support these functionalities, the modems are going to be equipped with EvoLogics intelligent Networking Software (EviNS) Framework giving the opportunity for easy integration of project-specific algorithms and protocols direct on board of the modem’s processor. In particular, each AUG will be equipped not with one, but with two modems, one on the top and one below each AUG (one locking downwards and another one upwards). A corresponding **algorithm implemented into EviNS framework** is currently developed for providing the flexibility in selection of positioning aid sides, i.e. **for positioning of AUGs either in relation to ASWG or to benthic station, or to both simultaneously**.

Regarding **USBL-positioning**, the peculiarity of the USBL-modem will consist in the flexibility to operate in numerous selectable/adjustable modes including measurements of **bearing and elevation**

angles in absence of bi-directional signal exchange, thus **providing silent positioning** of underwater assets, as well as reduction of active signalling and minimizing hardware infrastructure. This functionality will require **implementation of additional protocols of the USBL-modem** and integration of the newly developed features into the modems of all RAMONES vehicles.

1.2 Communications

This is expected that underwater vehicles and instruments will communicate in a coordinated manner. Particularly communication with the γ -Sniffers is going to be enabled to ensure in-mission coordination possibility. Continuous radioactivity monitoring will include the AI-based module providing detection of abnormal radioactivity levels which will have an impact on the behaviour of the glider by affecting the planning operations of the vehicle. Particularly, the event of abnormal radioactivity will trigger communication with the master communication node, passing relevant information for further processing. Similarly, events detected at the benthic lab will be evaluated by the decision-making mechanisms onboard to adjust the instrument array, direct the sensors to an area of interest, as well as **trigger communication with the master node**. Obviously, the realisation of such a task will require **advanced data networking** approaches (particularly, based on the EviNS Framework) which will be implemented on board of each modem processing platform.

Collaborative analysis and data exchange between robotic assets through underwater acoustics and data-driven behaviour of the underwater vehicles is based on integration of the off-shelf acoustic modems, which are currently further developed for facilitating the **operation in different networking scenarios**. E.g., "**negotiations**" of the AUGs, e.g. for joining the mission (that represents a data-driven event), requires operative (on-line) data exchange, that can be solved by means of the underwater acoustic network, capable for **finding the shortest (fastest) route for data exchange**. This and other novel features are planned to be developed for inclusion into the EviNS framework.

1.3 Modem Emulator

Since systems integration and validation tasks require comprehensive experimenting with many system components, the project partners will be **supplied (in the first project phase) with simulating software in order to avoid frequent at-sea testing** and thus to reasonably concentrate the available resource onto key tasks of the project. For example, tasks devoted to network communications and to the integration of the Navigation, Motion Planning and Control, Positioning and Communication systems, as well as to the assessment of their performance will be done in simulation first. Only after successful completion of all integration tasks at the simulators, the consortium will start with real

(expensive) at-sea trials. For this purpose, two software platforms will be connected: i) NetMarSyS - A Tool for the Simulation and Visualization of Distributed Autonomous Marine Robotic Systems, proprietary of IST-ID, and ii) the Software Emulator of Acoustic Network of Evologics.

In order to solve the abovementioned tasks, several innovative functionalities of the standard acoustic equipment will have to be developed.

Particularly, besides reliability and accuracy, the development of the T2.1 is focused on delivering wide (virtually unlimited) scalability of the RAMONES system to a sufficiently large number of AUGs, as well as, on reducing the amount of acoustic “signalling”, i.e. due to newly proposed “silent” positioning and event-driven interrogation algorithms, thus also decreasing the required energy and extending the endurance of autonomous operations.

Currently the underwater acoustic (UWA) modems are further developed to facilitate the following innovative project-specific functionalities:

- distribution of data streams among different underwater platforms on distances of up-to 3 km, i.e. among AUGs, glider, and benthic station,
- data networking in different scenarios (with several media-access and network layers): advanced data networking for distribution data in network, e.g. after triggering communication with the master node or with the benthic lab or with one of the AUGs,
- networked "negotiations" of the AUGs with operative data exchange network, capable for finding the shortest (fastest) route for data exchange, or for finding the least energy consuming route for data exchange, or for finding the safest route for data exchange,
- implementation of inter-vehicle communication protocols for cooperative navigation of the AUGs, e.g. with measuring mutual ranges and/or bearings among vehicles, providing: a) localisation by means of USBL “synchronous” uni-directional transmissions and/or “asynchronous” bi-directional transmissions); b) synchronous range-only localisation; and c) “silent” USBL-based localisation through triangulation using measurements of the USBL antenna, e.g. based on measurements of bearing and elevation angles in absence of bi-directional signal exchange,
- positioning of AUGs either in relation to ASWG or to benthic station, or to both simultaneously,
- implementation of the algorithm for LBL positioning of underwater equipment by means of ASWG executing synthetic positioning algorithm,
- full-functional support of the simulation software.

The peculiarity of the USBL-modem will consist in the flexibility to operate in numerous selectable/adjustable modes including measurements of bearing and elevation angles in absence of bi-directional signal exchange, thus providing silent positioning of underwater assets, as well as reduction of active signalling and minimizing hardware infrastructure.

On the other side silent positioning algorithms require identical time reference, what is possible only in case of synchronous operation of their clocks.

This important question was investigated in the scope of Task 2.1.

Particularly, relatively inexpensive commercial quartz clocks, which are mostly used in the Evologics modems, were evaluated in the sense of their capability for time keeping during long operation of the modems autonomously underwater.

The experimental results of time keeping were compared to results obtained earlier for expensive atomic clocks. On the results that were obtained in the scope of the project, several improvements were proposed for possible future use of unexpensive commercial quartz clocks in tasks requiring rather accurate time keeping.

Particularly, the long-term behaviour of standard quartz clocks (used in the acoustic modems) was thoroughly investigated, which provided the possibility to calibrate the mutual clock drifts and to use the calibration data for rather accurate and use of the standard modems in different positioning tasks specific for the project.

Two large experiments were carried out by Evologics in underwater acoustic environment of practical interest in August-September 2021.

These experiments were carried out thanks to access for selected users to marine robotics infrastructures, provided by NATO STO Centre for Maritime Research & Experimentation (CMRE) in the scope of Transnational Access (TNA) activities in the area of EU Marine Robotics (Marine robotics research infrastructure network) funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 731103.

One of the experiments was on the investigation of mutual clock drifts in long observation intervals.

Another experiment was on the investigation of synchronisation of the modems using hydro-acoustic links.

The descriptions of the experiments and the achieved results follow.

2. Experiments on mutual drifts of standard clocks used in standard UWA modems

2.1 Description of tests

Multiple tests included evaluation of the performance of underwater acoustic networking methods implemented as part of a modem's software in shallow waters and in different scenarios, particularly for synchronisation of the modems through hydro-acoustic link.

The networks were used for transmission of different types of data: instant messages, synchronous instant messages, special requests (e.g. sequence of data packets for execution of clock synchronisation procedure via hydro-acoustic link).

The UWA modems that were used in the tests were industrial modems model S2CR18/34.

The first group of test results provided the possibility to estimate mutual clock drifts between all pairs of hydro-acoustic modems involved in the tests. Clock drifts demonstrated to be nearly linear staying in the order of 1 microsecond per second, slightly depending on water temperature. The clock drifts of different modem pairs can differ within one order of magnitude.

In conditions of shallow waters, the communication channel can strongly vary (multipaths arrivals can vary on the strengths in the range of tens of decibels); so that the receiver can synchronise itself to different multipath arrivals within the time interval of two neighbouring data symbols. In this case the measurements of the time interval between two successive data symbols can demonstrate abrupt jumps. A median rejecting filter seems to be good option for filtering such jumps (outliers).

The second group of tests (on modem's clocks synchronisation through hydro-acoustic channel) demonstrated that clock synchronisation can be done with accuracy of milliseconds range within one single synchronisation attempt. Averaging clock skews estimates over time can rapidly increase the synchronisation accuracy. Apart of synchronisation between modems, also host computers connected to the modems can be synchronised (notifying them with RTO messages containing estimated real time offsets). Being based on these results further developments on an advanced synchronisation process of the modems in a network can be developed in a short time.

2.2 Tests outcomes

First experiment consisted in messages exchange between all network nodes for estimation of their mutual clock drifts. The direct measurements of the clock drifts can be used by a network of

multiple UWA modems during an autonomous operation for their mutual synchronisation, e.g. for implementation of a customised MAC layer scenarios or “silent” and scalable positioning algorithms.

In this experiment the special type of messages of Evologics modems – Synchronous Instant Messages (IMS) – were used.

The messages were broadcasted by each network node periodically to every other node of the network each three seconds (1 hour each node) starting a new cycle every four hours with different signal parameters (signal source level changed within 20 dB range, from 186 dB down to 166 dB re 1 uPa).

The figures below demonstrate main results of the experiments.

Fig. 1 shows the clock drift of the modem #143 in relation to the clock of modem #141. Modem #141 broadcasted IMS every 3 seconds to modem #143 during 1-hour time slot on 21 August 2021 (here the second cycle of signal exchange is presented). Estimated clock drift was $0.32 \mu\text{s/s}$ (1.15 ms per hour). Such clock drift can be too large for many underwater applications requiring synchronous operations of several instruments distributed underwater without any wired connection between them. From this reason the investigation of clock drift behaviour between many different modems and a design of wireless underwater clock synchronisation algorithms is desired. Fig. 2 shows the conditions of acoustic signals reception by the modem #143.

The distance between the modems is 397 m. The RSSI varied from -66 dB to -57 dB re 1 V on the output of the transducer preamplifier. Comparing to noise intensity of about $-90 \dots -93 \text{ dB}$ (re 1 V) the SNR of the received signal was better than 24 dB. The Signal Integrity was between 110 and 297 units. When relating these units to number 512 (i.e. to the number of samples in each data symbol), the correlation coefficient of the received signal (in relation to reference signal) could be estimated: in this case the correlation coefficient was between 0.21 and 0.58. The relative speed between the modems (estimated through Doppler coefficient, calculated during signals reception) was between -5 and $+12 \text{ cm/s}$. The mean value of the relative speed (the bias) was 2.5 cm/s , what corresponds to the clock drift of the modem #143 in relation to clock of the modem #141.

Fig. 1 shows several outliers (below the sold line). These outliers correspond to data symbols, in which the second multipath arrival was much stronger than the first one. (In cases, when the first arrival of the impulse response was weaker for more than 10 dB in relation to the dominating arrival, this was ignored by the processing unit with parameter settings used in the tests).

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Figure 1. Clock skew: modem #141 broadcasts to modem #143 for 1 hour, on 21.08.2021, second cycle

Figure 2. Reception conditions at modem #143 during 1-hour broadcasting of modem #141 (second cycle)

Similarly, Fig. 3 shows the clock drift of the modem #143 in relation to the clock of modem #141. Modem #141 broadcasted IMS every 3 seconds to modem #143 during 1-hour time slot on 21 August 2021 (here the first cycle of signal exchange is presented).

Fig. 4 shows the conditions of acoustic signals reception by the modem #143. In this cycle of data exchange the RSSI was in average 12 dB smaller than in the test above, staying between -73 and -82 dB (re 1V). Signal Integrity was smaller, between 90 and 238 units (correlation coefficient with the reference signal was 0.18 ... 0.46). Relative speed between the modems (estimated through Doppler coefficient, calculated during signals reception) was between -5 and $+11$ cm/s. Mean value of the relative speed was 2.8 cm/s, what corresponded to the clock drift of modem #143 in relation to clock of the modem #141. Estimated clock drift was $0.37 \mu\text{s/s}$ (1.33 ms per hour).

Fig. 3 shows many outliers (above the trend line representing in the first order the straight line). Dominating multipath arrival was the third one in the sequence of „significant“ arrivals („significant“ means not less than -10 dB in relation to the dominant one). The outliers corresponded to data symbols, which were received when 1st or 2nd multipath arrival was interpreted as „significant“, i.e. not weaker than 10 dB relatively to the dominant one.

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Figure 3. Clock skew: modem #141 broadcasts to modem #143 for 1 hour, on 21.08.2021, first cycle

Figure 4. Reception conditions at modem #143 during 1-hour broadcasting of modem #141 (first cycle)

Fig. 5 shows the clock drift of modem #143 in relation to clock of modem #141, (modem #141 broadcasted IMS every 3 second to modem #143 during 1-hour time slot on 21 August 2021 (here the third cycle of signal exchange is presented).

Fig. 6 shows the conditions of acoustic signals reception by modem #143. In this cycle of data exchange the RSSI was the largest in relation to tests described above, staying in the range $-54 \dots -58$ dB (re 1 V). Signal Integrity was also much larger, between 195 and 299 units (correlation coefficient with the reference signal was $0.38 \dots 0.58$). The relative speed between the modems was between -4 and $+9$ cm/s. Mean value of the relative speed (the bias) was 2.7 cm/s. Estimated clock drift was $0.34 \mu\text{s/s}$ (1.22 ms per hour).

Fig. 5 shows several outliers (below the trend line). The outliers correspond to data symbols, in which the second multipath arrival was at least 10 dB stronger than the direct (first) arrival.

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Figure 5. Clock skew: modem #141 broadcasts to modem #143 for 1 hour, on 21.08.2021, third cycle

Figure 6. Reception conditions at modem #143 during 1-hour broadcasting of modem #141 (third cycle)

The test results demonstrate that

1. Implementation of linear regression algorithm seems also to be good option for accurate estimation of the clock drifts. Clock drift is nearly linear. This means that even in conditions of changing water temperature (within several hours after sunset and after sunrise), the mutual clock drift doesn't demonstrate any significant change. Variation around linear drift is appr. $0.1 \mu\text{s}$.
2. Mutual clock drifts can be experimentally estimated with the accuracy of about 0.03 ppm. In case of autonomous operation of modems with quartz clocks, the accumulation of clock error about $3\text{e-}8$ s per second will lead to accumulation of distance measurement errors of about 0.05 m per 1000 s seconds. For silent positioning over very long time such time keeping accuracy is poor. But for positioning tasks including episodic bi-directional message exchange, e.g. each several hundred or thousand seconds, the estimated time keeping accuracy can be sufficient.
3. The clock drift rates ($0.31 \mu\text{s/s}$, $0.34 \mu\text{s/s}$, $0.37 \mu\text{s/s}$) in all tests between modems #143 and #141 are similar. Small differences can be explained due to different temperatures of the environment (depending on time of the day in which the tests were run).
4. In conditions of shallow waters, the communication channel can strongly vary (multipaths arrivals can vary in the range of tens of dBs); so that modem receivers can synchronise themselves to different multipaths arrivals in two neighbouring data symbols. A median rejecting filter seems to be good option for filtering outliers.

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Other test results (Fig.7 – Fig.12) are demonstrated for IMS exchange between the modems #237 and #141 (when modem #237 broadcasted IMSs to modem #141 for 1 hour, on the same day, 23.08.2021).

The results are similar. The conclusions can be made the same.

Figure 7. Clock skew: modem #237 broadcasts to modem #141 for 1 hour, on 23.08.2021, first cycle

Figure 8. Reception conditions at modem #141 during 1-hour broadcasting of modem #237 (first cycle)

Figure 9. Clock skew: modem #237 broadcasts to modem #141 for 1 hour, on 23.08.2021, second cycle

Figure 10. Reception conditions at modem #141 during 1-hour broadcasting of modem #237 (second cycle)

Figure 11. Clock skew: modem #237 broadcasts to modem #141 for 1 hour, on 23.08.2021, third cycle

Figure 12. Reception conditions at modem #141 during 1-hour broadcasting of modem #237 (third cycle)

3. Experiments on clock synchronisation via underwater acoustic channel

The results of the tests above were used for development of the macro command for inclusion in the standard set of AT-commands of the UWA modems.

The command obtained the abbreviation AT%SYNC for synchronisation of two modems using underwater acoustic communication.

Fig. 13 illustrates an example of using AT%SYNC command for synchronizing the clocks of two host PCs, each interfaced with an underwater acoustic modem.

Figure 13. Real Time Clock Synchronization process

The table below demonstrates the implementation details of the macro command execution during communication between modem #144 and modem #237 (test on 23-08-2021).

AT%SYNC,1,10 SENDSTART,1,ims,163840,0 SENDEND,1,ims,1822242270,163840 SENDSTART,1,ims,163840,0 SENDEND,1,ims,1823359419,163840	RECVSTART RECVEND,1803906552,172058,-73,146 USBLANGLES,1325390695.611319,1325390695.34 3094,4,- 2.7566,0.0586,1.2881,0.0497,3.0849,0.1398,- 1.4729,-73,146,0.0192 USBLPHYD,1325390695.611619,1325376001.9200 01,4,1,-11183,30644,12636,-23605,-41924,- 13034,-18011,36600
RECVSTART RECVEND,1824204403,188534,-73,140	SENDSTART,4,ims,182272,455228 SENDEND,4,ims,1804606554,182272

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USBLPHYD,1325390715.880204,1325376001.9098 10,1,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0	SENDSTART,4,ims,182272,307876 SENDEND,4,ims,1805206553,182272
SENDSTART,1,ims,163840,0 SENDEND,1,ims,1824472817,163840 SENDSTART,1,ims,290816,144431 SENDEND,1,ims,1825672819,290816	RECVSTART RECVEND,1806137102,172057,-73,143 USBLANGLES,1325390697.871659,1325390697.59 5141,4,- 2.7608,0.0541,1.2919,0.0542,3.0866,0.1386,- 1.4727,-73,143,0.0194 USBLPHYD,1325390697.871953,1325376001.9200 02,4,1,-11158,30635,12487,-23950,-41924,- 13123,-18242,36510
RECVSTART RECVEND,1826434950,188534,-73,139	SENDSTART,4,ims,182272,453270 SENDEND,4,ims,1806837104,182272 SENDSTART,4,ims,182272,286096 SENDEND,4,ims,1807437103,182272
SENDSTART,1,ims,290816,156403 SENDEND,1,ims,1826872820,290816 SENDSTART,1,ims,290816,152877 SENDEND,1,ims,1828072821,290816	RECVSTART RECVEND,1808537103,299049,-72,147 USBLANGLES,132539700.366869,1325390699.969 951,4,- 2.7570,0.0589,1.2882,0.0475,3.0857,0.1374,- 1.4732,-72,147,0.0200 USBLPHYD,1325390700.367170,1325376001.9200 01,4,1,-11159,30657,12592,-23508,-41787,- 12760,-18045,36428 RTO,18706309
RECVSTART RECVEND,1828834950,290856,-74,144 USBLPHYD,1325390720.581697,1325376001.9098 09,1,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0 %SYNC,1,18706309,496.597,-74,144	SENDSTART,4,ims,282624,142729 SENDEND,4,ims,1809237105,282624 SENDSTART,4,ims,282624,212858 SENDEND,4,ims,1809837105,282624
SENDSTART,1,ims,290816,125019 SENDEND,1,ims,1829272823,290816	RECVSTART RECVEND,1810151415,34268,-67,42

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	<p>RECVSTART RECVEND,1810937112,299049,-73,155 USBLANGLES,1325390702.750907,1325390702.36 9920,4,- 2.7128,0.0752,1.2452,0.0278,3.0870,0.1381,- 1.4739,-73,155,0.0222 USBLPHYD,1325390702.751205,1325376001.9200 01,4,1,-11097,30664,12756,-22425,-41987,- 13146,-18049,36490 RTO,18704441</p>
<p>RECVSTART RECVEND,1830634969,290856,-73,136 RECVSTART RECVEND,1831234963,290856,-73,162</p>	<p>SENDSTART,4,ims,282624,163023 SENDEND,4,ims,1811637114,282624 SENDSTART,4,ims,282624,212931 SENDEND,4,ims,1812237114,282624</p>
<p>AT%SYNC,1,10 SENDSTART,1,ims,163840,0 SENDEND,1,ims,2131631895,163840 SENDSTART,1,ims,290816,149733 SENDEND,1,ims,2132831897,290816</p>	<p>RECVSTART RECVEND,2113296323,172062,-74,186 USBLANGLES,1325391004.989279,1325391004.72 7169,4,- 2.7598,0.0695,1.3015,0.0488,3.0922,0.1473,- 1.4629,-74,186,0.0243 USBLPHYD,1325391004.989575,1325376001.9200 01,4,1,-10940,32300,12394,-24417,-41976,- 13392,-18567,36495</p>
<p>RECVSTART RECVEND,2133594055,188535,-73,154</p>	<p>SENDSTART,4,ims,182272,449990 SENDEND,4,ims,2113996324,182272 SENDSTART,4,ims,182272,311598 SENDEND,4,ims,2114596325,182272</p>
<p>SENDSTART,1,ims,290816,159188 SENDEND,1,ims,2134031899,290816 SENDSTART,1,ims,290816,154280 SENDEND,1,ims,2135231900,290816</p>	<p>RECVSTART RECVEND,2115696320,299048,-74,200 USBLANGLES,1325391007.521599,1325391007.12 7817,4,-</p>

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	2.7623,0.1066,1.3064,0.0133,3.0929,0.1482,- 1.4642,-74,200,0.0239 USBLPHYD,1325391007.571524,1325376001.9200 03,4,1,-9334,32249,14107,-22712,-41975,-13411,- 18247,36796 RTO,18707319
RECVSTART RECVEND,2135994054,290857,-74,168 USBLPHYD,1325391027.731708,1325376001.9098 08,1,0,0,0,0,0,0,0,0 %SYNC,1,2878,496.615,-74,168	SENDSTART,4,ims,282624,124351 SENDEND,4,ims,2116396321,282624 SENDSTART,4,ims,282624,192328 SENDEND,4,ims,2116996322,282624
SENDSTART,1,ims,290816,125030 SENDEND,1,ims,2136431902,290816	RECVSTART RECVEND,2117321720,34315,-71,36 RECVSTART RECVEND,2118096331,299048,-74,197 USBLANGLES,1325391009.933926,1325391009.52 7798,4,- 2.7656,0.1110,1.3111,0.0076,3.0912,0.1471,- 1.4635,-74,197,0.0237 USBLPHYD,1325391009.934221,1325376001.9200 01,4,1,-9265,32585,14171,-22666,-41774,-13373,- 18442,36700 RTO,18705297
RECVSTART RECVEND,2137794062,290857,-74,182 RECVSTART RECVEND,2138394059,290857,-74,186	SENDSTART,4,ims,282624,199017 SENDEND,4,ims,2118796333,282624 SENDSTART,4,ims,282624,197480 SENDEND,4,ims,2119396332,282624

Modem #144 (left column) starts AT%SYNC (text in blue). After exchanging the AT commands with modem #237 (right column), it generates the notification %SYNC,1,18706309,496.597,-74,144, where the number 18706309 is the time offset between communication modems in microseconds. Repeating the synchronisation process second time, modem #144 generates the next notification

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%SYNC,1,2878,496.615,-74,168. The number 2878 is also time offset in microseconds, what is however calculated in relation to the time that was synchronised in the previous sync process.

In this series of tests, the command AT%SYNC was executed periodically, every 300 seconds. Not every time the command exchange was successfully completed. However, taking into account that full duration of the test was 4 hours, this was not only possible to estimate the time offset, but also to estimate an average clock drift between modems #237 and #144 over time. The list of successfully completed synchronisation processes below shows the clock offsets estimated in different time instants:

%SYNC,1,18706309,496.597,-74,144

%SYNC,1,2878,496.615,-74,168

%SYNC,1,2012,496.597,-72,142

%SYNC,1,2401,496.622,-71,129

%SYNC,1,-46,496.622,-71,124

%SYNC,1,232,496.618,-75,125

%SYNC,1,5645,496.610,-73,165

%SYNC,1,-2288,496.598,-73,211

%SYNC,1,2890,497.767,-69,214

%SYNC,1,-62,497.762,-70,214

%SYNC,1,2319,497.759,-68,227

Entire Clock Offset = 2878 + 2012 + 2012 + 2401 – 46 + 232 + 5645 – 2288 + 2890 – 62 = 15674 mcs.

Relating this value to 4 hours, the Clock Skew can be obtained:

Clock Skew = Entire Clock Offset (mcs) / Experiment Length (s) = 15674 / 14400 = 1.08 mcs/s.

Important result consists in the fact that this clock skew corresponds to clock skew measured in the previous tests with IMS exchange between modems #237 and #144. This means that executing several successful synchronisation processes the clock drift (clock skew) estimation can be accurately done.

This group of tests (on modem's clocks synchronisation through hydro-acoustic channel) demonstrated that

1. Clock offset estimation. i.e. clock synchronisation through underwater acoustic channel can be done with accuracy of millisecond range within one single synchronisation attempt.

2. Averaging clock skews estimates over time can rapidly increase the synchronisation accuracy and provide an accurate estimation of mutual clock drift of the communication modems.
3. Apart of synchronisation between modems, also host computers connected to the modems can be synchronised to the modem time reference (notifying them with RTO messages containing estimated real time offsets).
4. Providing that clock drifts are linear (as demonstrated above) and measuring all mutual clock drifts of all acoustic network participants (UWA modems), a table of mutual clock drifts (with accuracy of about 0.03 ppm) can be prepared, saved and used for a long time of autonomous modem operation.
5. Mutual clock drifts, estimated with the accuracy of about 0.03 ppm, are not sufficiently good for using the industrial UWA modems (equipped with standard quartz clocks) for executing autonomous operations during many days or weeks.
6. However, there are tasks, in which UWA modems must operate in a hybrid mode, i.e. most of time in “silent” mode, and episodically in active bi-directional data exchange mode. In such tasks the table of mutual clock drifts (with accuracy of about 0.03 ppm) can be effectively used for sufficiently accurate synchronisations of acoustic network participants (UWA modems).

3.1 Selection of the models of UWA modems

Since the geometrical size of the RAMONES system is anticipated to be less than 3 km in each dimension, the UWA modems, which were selected for application in the project, belong to the series S2C 18/34 of Evologics production.

Particularly the hardware solution which is selected for integration into RAMONES AUGs and the ASWG vehicles is based on OEM version of the modem S2CM 18/34 OEM.

The modem has the following characteristics (**Error! Reference source not found.**):

- operating depth: 2000 m,
- frequency band: 18 - 34 kHz,
- transducer beam pattern is nearly omnidirectional,
- acoustic connection: data rate via acoustics: up to 13.9 kbit/s,
- bit error rate less than 10^{-10} ,
- host interface: Ethernet or RS-232,
- interface connectors: up to 4 connectors,
- power:

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- stand-by mode: 2.5 mW,
- listen mode: 5 - 285 mW,
- receive mode: 0.8 W,
- transmit modes: 2.8 W (1000 m range),
8 W (2000 m range),
35 W (3000 m range),
65 W (max. available),
- power supply: external 24 VDC (or 12 VDC), or
internal rechargeable battery 5 Ah (or 10 Ah).

Figure 14. Underwater acoustic modem S2CM18/34 OEM

The modem with USBL antenna (USBL-modem) will have similar characteristics related to its communication capabilities. Additionally, in relation to its positioning capabilities, the USBL-modem will have following characteristics:

- slant range accuracy: 0.01 m,
- bearing resolution 0.1 deg,
- nominal SNR 10 dB.

As demonstrated in the experimental section of this report, one of the most important options of the modem must be synchronous operation with other modems of the network.

Since there is a number of positioning and communications modes are anticipated to developed and tested in the scope of the RAMONES project, the decision was met to include both possibilities of the modems synchronisations:

- first group of the comms & positioning modes will be based on the usage of industrial UWA modems with standard quartz clocks due to experimental estimation of all mutual clock drifts of the network (tables on the mutual drifts) at the beginning on each autonomous mission, as well as on the corresponding algorithms capable for clocks resynchronisation during bidirectional data exchange between the modems in the mission, as well as for using the mutual clock drifts (tables on the mutual drifts) for keeping the UWA modems synchronised during their autonomous operation underwater;
- second group of the comms & positioning modes will be based on the usage of improved/experimental UWA modems equipped with non-standard low-drift clocks (atomic clocks), which will have to be only disciplined and synchronised before the autonomous mission on the surface (or on the shore), and then used autonomously underwater during a long time (at least several days or a week) without any need for re-synchronisation before their return to the surface (with anticipated low drift rate of less than 0.1 ms per day).

3.2 Requirements on hardware to UWA USBL-modems

To achieve all the aims of the RAMONES project, the requirements on hardware to UWA modems and USBL-modems are formalised in following short descriptions:

3.2.1 Surface vehicle (ASWG)

- 1 x S2C R Hydroacoustic Modem w/USBL 18/34H strem; OEM (eth+pps ;ahrs)
- Housing Material: OEM Version - no housing
- Antenna Type: Streamlined USBL
- Antenna connection Type: Cable mounted antenna with Impulse LPMIL connector
- Antenna cable length: 1.5 m
- Power Supply Type: External
- Additional Interface: PPS-in line (timekeeping via 1PPS),
- Power Supply Voltage: 12 VDC (14.4 V)
- Interface connector Layout 1: Ethernet+PPS-IN+Power
- AHRS Sensor: Built-in
- Bulkhead connector for USBL transducer (Impulse; 8-wire) * bulkhead connector, sealing, washer and nut,
- Mechanical adapter for ASWG centerboat.

3.2.2 Gliders (AUG)

2 x S2C R **Hydroacoustic Modem w/USBL 18/34** strem; OEM (eth+pps ;ahrs atomic)

- Housing Material: OEM Version - no housing
- Antenna Type: Streamlined USBL
- Antenna connection Type: Cable mounted antenna with Impulse LPMIL connector
- Antenna cable length: 0.6 m
- Power Supply Type: External
- Interface: Ethernet
- Additional Interface: PPS-out line (timekeeping for AUG host computer)
- Advanced Timekeeping: CSAC - Atomic Clock
- Power Supply Voltage: 24 VDC
- Interface connector Layout 1: Ethernet+PPS-IN+PPS-OUT+Power
- AHRS Sensor: Built-in
- Bulkhead connector for USBL transducer (Impulse; 8-wire) * bulkhead connector, sealing, washer and nut.

2 x S2C R **Hydroacoustic Modem 18/34 OEM** (eth+pps)

- Housing Material: OEM Version - no housing
- Antenna connection Type: Cable mounted antenna with Impulse LPMIL connector
- Antenna cable length: 0.6 m
- Power Supply Type: External
- Power Supply Voltage: 24 VDC
- Interface connector Layout 1: Ethernet+PPS-IN+Power.

3.2.3 Benthic station

1 x S2C R **Hydroacoustic Modem w/USBL 18/34 Titanium** (eth+pps ;2:rel ;b8m ;b6f ;3:rel ;3:b6f ;wake ;ahrs ;Li7.6Ah atomic)

- Housing Material: Titanium (max. depth 6000 m)
- Power Supply Type: Internal * Power Supply Voltage: 24 VDC
- Internal battery: Li-ion 7S2P 25.2V-7.6 Ah (191.5 Wh with BMS and charger)
- Primary connector type: Subconn BCR1508M
- Interface connector Layout 1: Ethernet+PPS-IN+Power

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- Interface connector Type 2: Subconn BCR1506F
- Interface connector Layout 2: Acoustic releaser
- Interface connector Type 3: Subconn BCR1506F
- Interface connector Layout 3: Acoustic releaser
- Wakeup-Module: Acoustic wake-up module (continuous power for CSAC)
- AHRS Sensor: Built-in
- Advanced Timekeeping: CSAC - Atomic Clock 1.0 30,500.00 € 30,500.00 € 9 . [S2C-310-02-S8F-O] S2C Cable (Subcon MCIL8F, eth+PPS-IN, 2 m)
- Cable connector 1: Subconn MCIL8F, Length: 2 m, Cable connector 2: open-wires
- S2C Releaser (Subconn MCIL6M, 2 m), Cable connector 1: Subconn MCIL6M, Length: 2 m.

3.2.4 Support vessel (mission control)

2 x S2C R **Hydroacoustic Modem w/USBL** 18/34 Delrin (eth+pps ;ahrs)

- Housing Material: Delrin (max. depth 200 m)
- Power Supply Type: External
- Additional Interface: PPS-in line (timekeeping via 2PPS)
- Power Supply Voltage: 24 VDC
- Primary connector type: Subconn FCR1508M
- Interface connector Layout 1: Ethernet+PPS-IN+Power
- AHRS Sensor: Built-in

2 x **Mounting Frame** for S2C USBL for

- USBL Antenna Type: HF Antenna
- Modem material: Delrin
- Connector configuration: Standard one connector
- Housing length: 200 mm
- Flange Type: 8er-Flange

2 x S2C **Cable** (Subcon MCIL8F, Ethernet RJ45, 25 m),

- Cable connector 1: Subconn MCIL8F
- Cable connector 2: RJ45; 4 mm power plugs
- Length: 25 m

8 x TTL to RS232 **converter PCB**

3.3 Synchronous single-range navigation

In optimal conditions, the USBL-modems installed on-board each node of the RAMONES system provide position fixes of the other nodes. However, it may happen that position fixes are not available for some period but slant ranges are still measured. In this sub-optimal situation, one solution is to resort to the so-called synthetic long baseline approach, whereby slant range measurements are collected overtime, as well as relative displacements, to construct an artificial long baseline, and then solve it for the current position. A more elegant alternative is to feed a tightly-coupled navigation filter directly with the available information. In this setting, proprioception sensors must provide the relative displacement of each node between consecutive slant range measurements. The latter are used to drive, nominally, the navigation error to zero, whereas the former is used to drive the system dynamics between consecutive time instants.

It is important to stress that, whereas in the optimal scenario with position fixes the system is typically observable, even assuming constant velocity models, in the sub-optimal single-range scenario the observability of the system depends on the relative motion of the nodes. In fact, the relative displacement vectors over a certain time window must span the 3-D space if the estimation error is to be driven to zero. Moreover, depending on the quantities to be estimated, namely the inclusion of the ocean currents, additional restrictions apply. For instance, the speed cannot be constant.

Considering the observability constraints and the type of vehicles at hand, it is clear that this setting should only be considered as a complementary feature to the main full USBL-model case. Indeed, the movement of the AUGs will typically be along long straight lines. Moreover, for optimal communication, the ASWG should stay close to the vertical of the AUGs, hence rich trajectories are not easily achieved.

Notwithstanding these limitations, it is worth pointing out that, even if rich trajectories are not available, the navigation error can still be partly bounded using synchronous slant range measurements.

3.4 USBL-based localisation through triangulation

In typical triangulation settings, a set of bearing/elevation measurements are obtained with respect to a certain point, and from these measurements, its localization is possible. In the RAMONES concept, the USBL may provide bearing/elevation between nodes without the burden of a two-way travel time operation mode. Similarly to single range navigation or synthetic LBL, if consecutive

bearing/elevation measurements are obtained, it is possible to devise an artificial triangulation setting, from which the position of the node can be retrieved. Likewise, observability conditions apply. However, these are less strict than for the single case, in the sense that, as long as the bearing/elevation measurements are non-collinear, the system is, in general, observable. An alternative to this setting, which essentially is the dual of the synthetic LBL but based on triangulation instead of trilateration, it is also possible to feed, in a tightly coupled navigation filter, the measurement information directly [Bat13].

An alternative to this concept is to take advantage of the depth sensor that is available in the underwater nodes of RAMONES, which restricts their position to horizontal planes. Thus, as long as the direction measurement is not horizontal, it is possible to pinpoint the position of the node in the plane using the bearing/elevation angles.

Cooperative navigation of “opportunity”

As it was seen, the envisioned concept for localization of the nodes of RAMONES, based on full USBL-modems mounted on each node, is quite flexible. In optimal conditions, position fixes are available, which readily allow for the localization of all nodes. In suboptimal conditions, either slant ranges or bearing/elevation angles may still be available. The envisioned cooperative navigation system should take advantage of the different sources of information. Typically, proprioception will provide the means to propagate the navigation information when USBL measurements are not available. When a USBL measurement is available (position fix, slant range, bearing/elevation angles, or depth), and possibly using communications, the cooperative navigation system should engage the appropriate navigation algorithm, in a typical Kalman-filter update step, to correct to error, effectively driving it to a vicinity of zero as long as all observability conditions are met.

3.5 Cooperative Control and Underwater Target Localization

RAMONES calls for the development and implementation of a number of systems for cooperative control to afford the surface and underwater robotic platforms the capability to manoeuvre in a concerted manner, either following a pre-defined mission plan or generating the plan on-line, over successive time windows, in response to episodic events. In preparation for future developments, and in the absence at this stage of access to the abovementioned platforms, preliminary work was done on the development and implementation of selected methods for cooperative control and underwater target localization, followed by real tests with the Medusa-class of autonomous marine vehicles that are property of IST. This has proven to be extremely useful in

terms of gaining valuable experience in the execution of the different steps involved in the design, evaluation, simulation, and real-time implementation of selected algorithms on the computers installed on-board the vehicles, fully equipped with motion and acoustic communication and ranging devices. Some of the solutions adopted are expected to transition to the systems that will permit the concerted operation of the RAMONES autonomous marine platforms. Among the systems developed, single vehicle path following took center stage because it is an enabling block for a type of multi-vehicle manoeuvres called cooperative path following.

Path following refers to the act of making a single vehicle converge to and move along a given spatial path, while tracking a desired along-path speed profile. In this context [Mau22, Hun22] contain a wealth of information on the design, implementation, and at-sea testing of a number of path following control algorithms, a subset of which is expected to be used in the scope of RAMONES. The next figures show a Medusa-class vehicle (figure 15), the general organization of the path following algorithm adopted (figure 16), and the types of trajectories obtained using a number of paths following algorithms (figure 17).

Figure 15. The Medusa-class of marine vehicles

Cooperative path following involves more than one vehicle, and can be briefly described as the process of making a number of possibly heterogeneous vehicles converge to desired paths, and at the same time adopt a desired inter-vehicle geometric formation pattern evolving at a common normalized along-path speed [Hun21, Reg21, Bra22].

Figure 16. Path following control system

Figure 17. Vehicle trajectories using different path following algorithms: experiments at sea demonstrating the performance obtained in the course of a lawnmowing manoeuver.

In the scope of the work done, the more complicated problem of cooperative distributed estimation and control of multiple autonomous vehicles for range-based underwater target localization and pursuit was addressed, yielding the solution described in [Hun21a]. Here, the problem of using single or multiple cooperative autonomous vehicles, called trackers, to localize and pursue an unknown underwater moving target using measurement of the ranges between the tracker(s) and the target was studied. At the motion planning level, each tracker is assigned a spatial-temporal (S-T) curve to track that is generated by the composition of two types of motion: along the target’s trajectory and on a path encircling the target. At the control level, we derived control laws for robust trajectory tracking and showed that under mild assumptions on the convergence of the target’s state estimate provided by a suitably designed filter, the tracker converges to and remains

in a desired vicinity of the target. For the case of multiple trackers, we proposed an efficient distributed estimation and control (DEC) strategy for the trackers that consider explicitly the constraints on the inter-tracker communication network. For this purpose, a distributed extended Kalman filter (DEKF) and a distributed control law for cooperative S-T curve tracking were developed to cooperatively pursue and localize the target. Using this setup, all trackers converge to a specified vicinity of the target while keeping an optimal tracker-target relative geometry that maximizes the range information acquired to estimate the target’s state. The stability of the complete closed-loop DEC system was analyzed rigorously and the efficacy of the proposed strategy was illustrated with extensive computer simulations for the 2-D and 3-D cases. The organization of the resulting system is shown in figure 18.

Special emphasis was placed on the use of event-driven communication strategies for cooperative motion control with a view to substantially reduce the amount of information exchanged among the heterogeneous vehicles. This will be key to the implementation of the cooperative operation of the RAMONES assets, which rely on low-band with data exchange over the acoustic channel.

Figure 18. A distributed estimation and control architecture for range-based underwater target localization and pursuit

The conceptual architecture described above was configured to solve the problem of Cooperative Simultaneous Target Localization and Pursuit (SLAP) using Multiple Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASVs). Several field trials were carried out involving multiple autonomous vehicles working in cooperation. Namely, two surface autonomous vehicles, called trackers, and an underwater autonomous vehicle, called target, have been employed. In this scenario, successful trials have been

carried out in which the two surface vehicles were operated in a collaborative manner to track and localize the underwater vehicle using acoustic range measuring devices.

The information gathered by the trackers can be used as navigation aid for the underwater vehicle or for localization and monitoring tasks. The results of the trial were quite encouraging in that the trackers could not only estimate the state of the target well but also converged smoothly to and maintained an optimal formation (in an estimation-theoretical context) with respect to the target, while manoeuvring within a desired vicinity of it. The field trials focused on the testing of a "cooperative distributed simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAP)" algorithm developed and implemented jointly by the DSOR group at IST Lisbon and UNED.

To test the SLAP algorithm, we used three Medusa-class vehicles (Medusa-red, black, and yellow) that are property of IST. The Medusa yellow acted as an underwater target while the other two vehicles (Medusa red and black) played the role of trackers. In this setup, the trackers communicated with each other using the WiFi-UDP protocol. The ranges from the trackers to the target were measured using acoustic devices manufactured by Evologics. Regarding the pursuit task, the two trackers were set to move behind the target and maintain a distance of approximately 15 meters to the target while keeping the relative position vectors from the trackers to the target orthogonal for optimal target state estimation purposes. The vehicles used are shown in Figure 19, while Figure 20 shows photos of the IST-ID team in the control room during the experiments.

Figure 19. The MEDUSA-Class vehicles capable of operating as ASVs or AUVs

Figure 20. The IST-ID Team in the control room during the experiments.

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Figure 21 shows the trajectories of the target (blue) and the trackers (white and red) in the operations console in a configuration where the trackers are not required to encircle the target, thus reducing tracker energy expenditure. In the context of RAMONES where only one tracker (the autonomous surface vehicle) will be used, the algorithms can be adapted to allow tracking of the evolution of the underwater gliders, albeit at the cost of having the surface unit executing richer “spatially exciting” manoeuvres.

Figure 21. The operations console showing the MEDUSA vehicle paths during a SLAP mission

The results obtained are now being analysed in detail in preparation for a joint UNED/IST-ID peer reviewed journal publication. Again, the experience acquired in the process of going from the laboratory to the real world using real vehicles will impact very positively the development of the RAMONES systems for cooperative navigation and control.

Cooperative Motion Planning

As mentioned before, the RAMONES project requires the concerted operation of an autonomous surface vehicle and 2 autonomous underwater gliders to detect and map the extent of radioactive sources underwater, in many cases by detecting the plumes of radon that will be emitted by the sources. For this purpose, and in order to avoid exhaustive search procedures which are extremely demanding in terms of energy, a two-step procedure will be adopted: i) off line cooperative motion planning taking into account any prior information on the location of the sources and plumes, albeit with a possibly large degree of uncertainty, which will set the baseline for an initial search procedure and ii) on-line adaptive, or event-driven motion planning, where the events are the occurrence of radioactivity levels above the background level. Work on the first strategy led to the development of a methodology for cooperative motion planning that relies on the use of Bernstein polynomial-based methods for solving optimal planning problems by incorporating explicitly temporal and energy-like constraints, as well as obstacle avoidance [Ber21, Kie22]. A software package has been developed to solve this type of problems. The work is currently being extended to deal with prior information on the location of underwater radioactive sources and respective plumes, where the uncertainty about the latter is captured in a probabilistic framework.

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